

EFFECTIVENESS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF ENRICHMENT ACTIVITIES IN GRADE 8 SCIENCE UTILIZING GUIDED INQUIRY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The research study dealt with the development, acceptability and effectiveness of the Enrichment Activity in Physics utilizing Guided Inquiry Experience Strategy in Teaching Grade 8 Science. The study made use of both descriptive and experimental methods utilizing pretest and posttest design, the respondents were the two handled sections of the researcher they are the Control and Experimental group of the study; each section is composed of sixty (60) students. Both groups were given the validated pretest and posttest before and after the topics were presented, to analyze the data gathered mean and standard deviation were used to measure mean scores of the experimental and control group. Dependent t-test was used to find out the significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental and control group while independent t-test was used to find out the significant difference between the posttest mean scores of both experimental and control group. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant increase on total posttest mean score of 50.27 on the experimental group and 36.06 on the control group compared to the 30.71 and 29.31 pretest mean scores of the experimental and control groups with respect to different topics.

Keywords: *Enrichment Activity in Physics, Guided Inquiry Experience, Development, Acceptability*

INTRODUCTION

Science and advancement in technology have affected the world in many significant ways. It is important that students examine Science and the emerging technology as endeavors with consequences for people and let them learn to relate their knowledge to the world beyond their classroom. Many teachers devote a disproportionate amount of time and energy to disciplining their class rather than managing their class. According to Bautista (2018) great teaching is an act of art. "Great artistic teaching relies not just on the mastery but also on application of foundational skills learned individually inside and outside the classroom through diligent study and observation and experience. There must be a carefully planned technique system of procedures, rules and routines that creates an atmosphere to learn individually or in-group.

The teacher is the key variable in the classroom that plays a significant role in learning. The teacher is the key variable inside the classroom and by giving them proper materials and instruments can lead enhanced learner's interactions, Gimeno (2010). The current pandemic situation imposed a challenge in school's preparation in the teaching-learning process to adopt in the new normal situation. In the abrupt change of the world with regards to education brought by pandemic situation it allows us to see the vulnerability of schools and how schools are affected in general in their curriculum implementation.

It also imposed a challenge among school leaders and teachers to be more resilient and innovative in the implementation of the teaching and learning process. The purpose of the study is to develop Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach in teaching. Inquiry is a tool scientist, and others use to ask questions about the natural world. In the context definition of inquiry, there exists a tension between the need to guide the learner, the need for direct teacher instruction and the role of the teacher in the learning process.

Guided Inquiry works best when the topic is less black and white, when successful performance depends on making judgments in a wide variety of situations. When poorly designed and facilitated, discovery learning will seem pointless, perhaps even manipulative; well managed and the result could be much deeper learning. As Carl Rogers once warned us, "Nothing that can be taught is worth learning."

The Guided Inquiry Approach begins with understanding the changes in the teacher's role which now include creating and supporting a coherent culture and community. According to Paloyo, (2012) teachers nowadays face problems like bigger classroom size and the sometimes learners who move to higher grade levels are not equipped with knowledge and skills necessary for learning.

Science Education is also facing various issues in terms of the best techniques and teaching methodologies to implement in order to produce students who are capable of solving real world problems. In the recent Programme for International Students

Assessment (PISA) results, the Philippines rank at the bottom for both Math and Science education and that, the Philippine educational system according to Congress needs some adjustments in curriculum and implementation.

Article XIV Section 10 of the Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines point out the importance of Science and Technology and its relevance to national growth and development. It states that: ***“Science and Technology are essential for national development and progress. The state shall give priority to research and development, invention and utilization and to science and technology, education training and services. It shall support indigenous, appropriate and self-reliant scientific and technological capabilities and their application to the country’s productive system on national life”.***

Philippine Education System is continuously evolving in order to produce students who are competent to be professionals who can contribute to national as well as global development. The government’s goal is to promulgate functional literacy for all Filipinos through the implementation of Enhanced Basic Educational Act started last school year 2012-2013. It adheres to the relevant skills and knowledge that learners should acquire. It states that: ***“The State shall give every student an opportunity to receive quality education that is globally competitive based on pedagogically sound curriculum that par with the international standards”.***

Therefore, a big accountability lies in the hands of the teachers in order to have a strong nation and to reach the expectation of everyone. Strong foundation of Education means strong nation. When teaching is stronger, students benefit with increased engagement that every country needs. In the current situation of the Philippine educational system, the need to innovate in terms of classroom teaching and curriculum implementation is necessary. The researcher having put that in mind was able to create a series of activities utilizing guided inquiry approach with a primary objective of enhancing science education skills among learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness and acceptability of the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the mean scores of the experimental and control groups as revealed by the pretest and posttest with respect to the following Learning Topics;
 - 1.1 Newton’s Three Laws of Motion;
 - 1.2 Work, Power and Energy;
 - 1.3 Heat and Temperature; and
 - 1.4 Electricity.
2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental and control groups with respect to the above-mentioned topics?
3. Is there a significant difference between the posttest mean scores of the experimental and control groups?

4. What is the level of acceptability of the enrichment activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach in teaching with respect to the following criteria;
 - 4.1 Objectives;
 - 4.2 Contents;
 - 4.3 Activities;
 - 4.4 Language and Style
 - 4.5 Graphics and Designs; and
 - 4.6 Usefulness.
 5. What are the feedback of the student and teacher respondents in the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach?
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METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness and acceptability of the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach at Tagumpay National High School Year 2021-2022. In accomplishing this study, experimental and descriptive methods of research were utilized. The respondents are the selected Grade 8 Science teachers in the Municipality of Rodriguez that will determine the validity and acceptability of the crafted materials used in the study. The student respondents in the control and experimental group are the two sections handled by the researcher in Grade 8 with the same sixty (60) number of students.

A qualitative approach was also employed using Focus Group Discussion for student respondents and interview using guided questionnaire for teacher respondents. Pretest and posttest were considered. According to Berdan (2008), experimental design is a technique that measures valid and reliable results of experimentation. Descriptive method of research is focused on the present condition, current practice and application, events and characteristics of individual in a wide sense in the analysis, classification, measurement and interpretation of the situation according to Bautista (2018).

It was utilized using an adapted and modified questionnaire checklist from Berdan (2008). It includes the criteria about Objectives, Contents Activities, Language and Style, Graphics and Designs and Usefulness. The descriptive – survey method was used to achieve the desired output of the study acceptability and effectiveness of the developed Enrichment Activities. It also used Focus Group Discussion among student respondents to determine the feedback of the students of the developed Enrichment Activities while an interview was made using guided questionnaire to determine the feedback of the teacher respondents on the developed material.

RESULTS

Mean scores of the Experimental and Control Groups as revealed by the Pretest and Posttest with respect to the Learning Topics: Newton's Three Laws of Motions, Work, Power and Energy, Heat and Temperature and Electricity.

Table 1
Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups as revealed by the Pretest and Posttest with respect to the Different Learning Topics

Topics	Experimental						Control					
	Pretest			Posttest			Pretest			Posttest		
	Mean	Sd	VI									
Newton's Three Laws of Motion	7.79	2.57	FS	11.65	2.85	S	8.06	2.20	S	8.08	3.00	S
Work, Power and Energy	7.60	2.75	FS	13.81	2.49	VS	6.74	2.29	FS	10.73	2.81	S
Heat and Temperature	7.50	2.53	FS	12.81	2.13	VS	6.84	2.16	FS	7.95	2.23	FS
Electricity	7.82	3.69	FS	12.02	3.18	VS	7.66	3.12	FS	9.31	2.91	S
Total	30.71	7.36	FS	50.27	6.11	VS	29.31	4.91	FS	36.06	5.64	FS

Legend: VS- Very Satisfactory FS- Fairly Satisfactory S- Satisfactory

T-test results between the Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control groups in different learning topics.

Table 2

T-test Results Between the Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

Topic		Mean	Sd	Mean Diff	t	df	Sig	H ₀ at 0.05	VI	Mean	Sd	Mean Diff	t	df	Sig	H ₀ at 0.05	VI
Newton's Three Laws of Motion	Pretest	7.98	2.7	3.71	15.6	64	0.00	R	S	8.06	2.2	0.02	0.1	61	0.95	FR	NS
	Posttest	11.69	2.9							8.08	3						
Work, Power and Energy	Pretest	7.68	2.8	6.15	22.2	64	0.00	R	S	6.74	2.3	3.98	12	61	0.00	R	S
	Posttest	13.83	2.5							10.7	2.8						
Heat and Temperature	Pretest	7.48	2.6	5.25	19.3	64	0.00	R	S	6.84	2.2	1.11	3.4	61	0.00	R	S
	Posttest	12.72	2.1							7.95	2.2						
Electricity	Pretest	7.75	3.6	4.15	20.5	64	0.00	R	S	7.66	3.1	1.65	4.1	61	0.00	R	S
	Posttest	11.91	3.2							9.31	2.9						
Total	Pretest	30.89	7.4	19.3	39.1	64	0.00	R	S	29.3	4.9	6.76	12	61	0.00	R	S
	Posttest	50.15	6.2							36.1	5.6						

Legend: S – Satisfactory NS – Not Satisfactory

T-test results between the Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups in different Learning Topics.

Table 3

T-test results between the Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

	Group	Mean	Sd	Mean Difference	T	df	Sig	Ho	VI
Newton's Three Laws of Motion	Experimental	11.65	2.85	3.57	6.78	122	.000	R	S
	Control	8.08	3.00						
Work, Power and Energy	Experimental	13.81	2.49	3.08	6.47	122	.000	R	S
	Control	10.73	2.81						
Heat and Temperature	Experimental	12.81	2.13	4.86	12.41	122	.000	R	S
	Control	7.95	2.23						
Electricity	Experimental	12.02	3.18	2.71	4.95	122	.000	R	S
	Control	9.31	2.91						
Total	Experimental	50.27	6.11	14.21	13.47	122	.000	R	S
	Control	36.06	5.64						

Legend: Satisfactory

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach.

Table 4

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Objectives

Objectives	Mean	VI
1. Aligned according to competency skill indicated in the curriculum.	4.84	VHA
2. Specified according to the subject matter.	4.81	VHA
3. Develop and engage the students to learn through the theory and self-activity.	4.72	VHA
4. Provide various learning activity to develop the knowledge and skill essential for student's development.	4.72	VHA
5. Connected with real life situation.	4.81	VHA
Average	4.78	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 5

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Contents

Contents	Mean	VI
1. Topics are relevant, interesting, self-motivating and at the level of understanding of students.	4.72	VHA
2. Structured in logical manner.	4.79	VHA
3. Main points are highlighted	4.84	VHA
4. Questions formed check the learner's understanding.	4.77	VHA
5. Establishes connections between theory and practical applications.	4.79	VHA
Average	4.78	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 6

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Activities

Activities	Mean	VI
1. Provide opportunities for guided active learning.	4.77	VHA
2. Provide real life situations.	4.70	VHA
3. Suit to the needs of the learners.	4.84	VHA
4. The activities match the objectives of the lesson	4.81	VHA
5. Provide opportunities for learners to master concepts in the learning areas focused.	4.91	VHA
Average	4.80	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 7

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Language and Styles

Language and Styles	Mean	VI
1. The directions give clear information about the topic.	4.81	VHA
2. Language used are basic, simple and easy to comprehend.	4.74	VHA
3. Language and structures used avoid misinterpretation.	4.84	VHA
4. Catchy titles were used	4.79	VHA
5. Language used is suitable to the ability of the students.	4.84	VHA
Average	4.80	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 8

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Graphics and Designs

Graphics and Designs	Mean	VI
1. The graphics are suitable to the learning areas.	4.86	VHA
2. The graphics and the pictures are clear and appropriate.	4.77	VHA
3. The font styles are appropriate.	4.81	VHA
4. The spacing is adequate.	4.84	VHA
5. The pictures and designs of the activities are appropriate and interesting.	4.78	VHA
Average	4.81	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 9

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Usefulness

Usefulness	Mean	VI
1. Enrichment activities are useful in understanding the different terminologies and concepts in different equations.	4.67	VHA
2. Enrichment activities provide competitive learning and prepare the students in actual application.	4.77	VHA
3. Enrichment activities are useful supplement to reinforce the transfer of learning.	4.88	VHA
4. Enrichment activities encourage one to work efficiently at his pace.	4.84	VHA
5. Enrichment activities magnifies the learning interest of the students.	4.88	VHA
Average	4.81	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Table 10

Composite table on the Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8

Aspect	Mean	VI
Objectives	4.78	VHA
Contents	4.78	VHA
Activities	4.80	VHA
Language and Styles	4.80	VHA
Graphics and Designs	4.81	VHA
Usefulness	4.81	VHA
Average	4.80	VHA

Legend: VHA – Very Highly Acceptable

Student and Teacher Feedback on the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach.

The following are the consolidated results on the feedback of the student-respondents who used the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach. The student respondents underwent Focus Group Discussion while the teacher respondents underwent an interview session with a questionnaire guide.

Student - Respondents Feedback

Enhances Learning. The majority of the students replied that the Enrichment Activities enhance their learning. It helps them become more knowledgeable on the topic, thus making them understand the topic the easiest possible way they can with the help of the guide questions and guidance of the teacher.

The topics are easy to understand. It implies that the student-respondents find the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science helpful in achieving the desired learning outcome. Thus, with the help of clear instructions and guidance from the teacher they find the activities included in the activity easy to understand. However, other students responded that the topics are not clear to them. However, there are students who respond negatively and stated that they find the topics quite hard to understand because instructions are not clear. Moreover, the results of those who answered “No” contribute only small portion of the class and does not affect the overall performance of the class as indicated in their posttest results.

Fun and Enjoyable. The majority of the student-respondents answered that the activities indicated on the topics Newton’s Three Laws of Motion and Electricity are the ones they enjoyed the most. They find the activities fun while learning with the guidance of their teacher. In addition, the Enrichment Activities used pictures that enabled them to understand the topic easily. Thus, making it caught their interest while having fun answering the questions indicated easily. However, those who answered “No” indicate that there are activities that required bigger space in order to perform effectively and that is why they didn’t find it enjoyable.

Guides to solving the problem. The student-respondents able to answer the questions indicated in each activity because the directions are clear with the help of the explanations of the teacher. Thus, the activities caught their attention in answering the guide questions easily.

Motivates the students to learn. The student-respondents indicate that the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science help them to learn the concept being presented and improve their knowledge and understanding on the topic. It made them gain more knowledge on the concept being presented. It also creates an atmosphere of creativity to them. In addition, it also improved their performance based on the results of their posttests. Moreover, it motivates them to learn more and improves their understanding on the lesson. These results indicate that the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science is

a useful tool in teaching the concept thus helping the teaching and learning process achieve its goal. The recommendations of the student respondents are as follows; More activities outside the classroom and provide activities that do not need materials that are expensive.

Teacher – Respondents Feedback

Stimulate students' knowledge on the topic. Most of the teachers responded that the graphics and designs used in the developed Enrichment Activities can stimulate the students' knowledge on the topics therefore leading to better understanding of the topics presented. However, other respondents find graphics and designs less attractive to learners thus they are suggesting for enhancement. Moreover, the step-by-step process of presenting the lesson and the clear and concise presentation of the lesson is a guided approach in learning by itself. Thus, making the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science a tool that gives guided learning to students.

Provide activities that prepare students for actual application. They believe that the activities included provides hands on task to the students does it provides hands on learning to them. Emphasis on providing HOTS questions promote critical thinking to students. In addition, the activities included in the developed Enrichment Activities provide actual and meaningful learning experience to students thus making it a device that provides learning and prepares students in actual application.

Using simple terms make students easy to comprehend the topics. The teachers' respondents positively respond that the used of simple terms in the activity will make students easily comprehend the topics included in the study. The activities used can stimulate students' curiosity and enhance transfer of learning through collaborative efforts. Moreover, the teacher respondents also include that the used of pictures and designs on the developed Enrichment Activities further enhances students' transfer of learning on the topics.

Magnifies interest on the topic. The use of simple terms and guide questions that promotes transfer of learning magnifies learning among students. In addition, the use of graphics and colorful designs will capture the imagination of the students that will stimulate them to answer the problem being given at their own pace. Teacher respondents also made emphasis on how the Enrichment Activities use the Word Sharp Up part in which students will familiarize first the terminologies to be used in the topics to be presented to them this somehow enhances learner's interest therefore helpful in magnifying their interest on the topics. The use of activities that provide learning connection between concept and real-life situation is an important part of the Enrichment Activities.

Systematic process of presenting the topics. The teacher-respondents find the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science is a helpful tool that guides students to learn the concept. Thus, the content of the Enrichment Activities provides a step-by-step process

of presenting the lesson/topics to the students implies that the Enrichment Activities adhere to its goal of providing Guided Learning to the students.

The Activities used motivate the learners to learn the topics. The activities included in the activity motivate students to learn the topics included in the study. The Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach is a tool that promotes transfer of learning to the students. It enhances their learning capacity as well as it magnifies their learning interest on the topics included in the study. However, other respondents replied that the Enrichment Activities should provide more activities outside the classroom setting.

DISCUSSION

Mean scores of the Experimental and Control Groups as revealed by the Pretest and Posttest with respect to the Learning Topics: Newton's Three Laws of Motions, Work, Power and Energy, Heat and Temperature and Electricity.

As revealed in table number 1, the performance of the experimental group improved from Fairly Satisfactory with a total mean score of 30.71 during the pretest to Very Satisfactory with a total mean score of 50.27 during the posttest. Furthermore, the decrease in the standard deviation from 7.36 to 6.11 indicates homogeneity in the performance of the group during the said tests. On the other hand, the control group sustained its Fairly Satisfactory performance with a slight increase in its total mean score from 29.31 during the pretest to 36.06 during the posttest and maintained its heterogeneity with the standard deviation increased from 4.91 to 5.64.

This means that the developed Enrichment Activities is an effective tool in improving the performance of the learners under the experimental group with respect to the learning topics indicated. This implies that the material is able to provide the basic instructions that enhance the learners' capabilities to learn the topics since their performance has improved. The improved performance of the students in using the Enrichment Activities also implies that the material helps them to understand the topics of Newton's Three Laws of Motions, Work Power and Energy, Heat and Temperature and Electricity and turns that understanding into learning. This was supported by the observation of Jimenez (2008), that the use of teachers made instructional materials in Chemistry increases the performance of the learners.

T-test results between the Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control groups in different learning topics.

It can be gleaned from the table 2 that there is a significant difference on the pretest and posttest scores in the experimental and control group in terms of the following topics Newton's Three Laws of Motion, Work, Power and Energy, Heat and Temperature and

Electricity with the obtained p-value of .000 which did not exceed the 0.05 level of significance thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

The significant difference on the performance of the students in the experimental group denotes that the used of the developed Enrichment Activities increases learners' performance in the different learning topics used in the study. In addition, the use of the developed Enrichment Activities improved learners' knowledge on the topics used.

The use of graphics and pictures are also contributory to the increase in the performance of the students that lead them to better understanding of the topics. Moreover, the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach adheres to the mandates of our Department of Education that teacher's 21st century role in the classroom setting is to facilitate the learning process and emphasize the importance of applications in the learning activities that simulate real life activities to better transfer of learning.

The findings imply that the developed Enrichment Activities helped improve the performance of the students in learning the different topics presented. This can also be attributed to the different illustrations of activities in which answers are being given and students will try to figure out the possible solutions arriving in the same answers as presented in the material this enhances the capability of the learners to think critically while the teacher guides them in solving the problem. This strengthens the statement of Parales (2013), who revealed that learners who are exposed to the developed materials in Physics have significant increase in their level of understanding the concept.

However, the result also reveals that the learners in the control group who used the Department of Education Learners Materials also have a significant increase in their posttest results compared to their pretest results. These results also show the effectiveness of the materials provided by the Department of Education. However, the developed Enrichment Activities made the experimental group perform better than the control group with respect to the following learning topics; Newton's Three Laws of Motion, Work, Power and Energy, Heat and Temperature and Electricity. With these results, it indicates that although the two materials are effective in increasing the posttest results of both groups (control and experimental), it revealed that the experimental group performs better than the control group.

T-test results between the Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups in different Learning Topics.

Table 3 presents the computed t-value of the experimental and control groups. Table 5 reveals that there is a significant difference between the results of the posttest of the experimental and control groups with the p – value not exceeding 0.05 level of significance in all learning areas thus, null hypothesis is rejected. The result implies that the developed Enrichment Activities is an effective tool in teaching the Physics concept to the leaners in the Grade 8 level. The material helps in the improvement of the students'

learning capacities and contributes to the improvement of the teaching and learning process.

It can be deduced from table 4 that most of the respondents agreed that the objectives given and stated in the developed Enrichment Activities are “Very Highly Acceptable” with an average mean of 4.78. This implies that the objectives in each topic in the developed Enrichment Activities are suited to the skills and abilities of the learners in learning the topics included in the study.

It also denotes that the objectives presented contribute to the learners’ performance in the teaching-learning process. On the other hand, it also implies the importance of stated objectives each in every topic presented that serve as a guide for both learners and teachers in accomplishing the desired outcome of the topics. This is also related to the statement of Bautista (2018) that specification of objectives is done to enhance lesson planning and to create possible behavioral outcomes among learners while making evaluation process much easier.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Objectives

It can be deduced from the table that most of the respondents agreed that the objectives given and stated in the developed Enrichment Activities are “Very Highly Acceptable” with an average mean of 4.78. This implies that the objectives in each topic in the developed Enrichment Activities are suited to the skills and abilities of the learners in learning the topics included in the study. It also denotes that the objectives presented contribute to the learners’ performance in the teaching-learning process. On the other hand, it also implies the importance of stated objectives each in every topic presented that serve as a guide for both learners and teachers in accomplishing the desired outcome of the topics. This is also related to the statement of Bautista (2018) that specification of objectives is done to enhance lesson planning and to create possible behavioral outcomes among learners while making evaluation process much easier.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Contents

It can be deduced from the table that the developed is “Very Highly Acceptable” in terms of Contents with an average mean of 4.78. This implies that the developed Enrichment Activities is an effective tool in teaching the Physics concept and its contents are contributory to the increased in the performance of the students in the different topics being used. The topics perhaps are interesting and are designed to easily grasp by the students at the level of their understanding.

The result of the score implies that the contents of the topics included in the study served as a guide for the teacher in accomplishing the teaching and learning process and made the topic understand by the students the easiest possible way the students can comprehend. Moreover, the results also suggest that the developed Enrichment Activities

are simple, structured in a logical manner and establishes connections between theory and practical applications these aids in developing higher order thinking skills among students. Related to the result of the study Palayo (2012) also stated that concept presented in the developed learning materials must be in the level of understanding of the learners in order to make them grasp it better. Thus, presentation of the contents must form highlighting the important concept that that are present in the evaluation process.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Activities

It can be gleaned from the table that the Activities in the developed Enrichment Activities are “Very Highly Acceptable” as evaluated by the experts with an obtained average mean 4.80. This means that the activities used in the material match the objectives of the lesson and suit the needs of the learners and it also provides opportunities for guided active learning. Thus, the material in particular aids in mastering the concepts in the learning areas focused.

The results indicate that the students are able to find the activities included in the developed material interesting and enjoyable. Thus, the students viewed the activities as a useful tool in easily learning the concept for it helps in participating actively in the teaching and learning process. Jimenez (2008) states that a variety of activities which lead the students to work well through a vivid presentation of topics and activities are the ways to attain the objectives of the lesson.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Language and Styles

It can be gleaned from the table that with respect to language and style, all items are interpreted “Very Highly Acceptable” as evaluated by the experts with an average mean of 4.80. The results reveal that the language and style used are basic, simple and easy to comprehend. In addition, it also presents clarity of usage of words that enables learners to comprehend the lesson easily.

Moreover, the results imply that the language and style used in the developed Enrichment Activities gives clear information to the students in performing the activities indicated. It shows that the language used is appropriate in understanding the concept included in the study. Soriano (2013) states that the language and style used in the study should be well matched to the mental capacity of the students. Furthermore, she added that in order for the developed materials to be effective it must use clear directions, which are easy to follow.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Graphics and Designs

It can be gleaned from the table that with respect to Graphics and Designs, all items are interpreted “Very Highly Acceptable” as evaluated by the experts with an average mean of 4.81. It reveals that the graphics and pictures used in the materials are clear and appropriate and suit the level of understanding of the student’s respondent. This implies that the pictures and designs used in the activities are appropriate and interesting. Moreover, the graphics and designs used are suitable to the learning areas or topics being used in the study. Bautista (2018) in her research study, “Development and Validation of Electronic Intervention Materials in Science for Grade 7.” states that in order for the material to become effective its graphics and designs must contain appropriate and colorful pictures, animations and must have interesting ways to meet learner’s need.

Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8 with respect to Usefulness

It can be deduced from the table that majority of the respondents agreed that the Usefulness of the developed material Enrichment Activities are “Very Highly Acceptable” with an average mean of 4.81 in which all criteria was interpreted by the respondents as “Very Highly Acceptable”. It implies that the developed Enrichment Activities is a useful instrument that helps reinforce the transfer of learning among student’s respondents. In addition, it also helps in understanding in learning the concepts used in different equations. Thus, the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science encourage students to work at their own pace that magnifies the learning of the students as indicated in the posttest results.

The result of the study is strengthened by the findings of Timado-Aran (2017) that the developed instructional is useful in attaining the objectives of higher results in Physics concept. The usefulness of the learning materials must be flexible to any size of the learning group and differences in learning time. It can be seen from table 9 that the teacher respondents assessed the developed Enrichment Activities as “Very Highly Acceptable” with an average mean score of 4.80 and it also have “Very Highly Acceptable” results in all Aspect.

Composite table on the Level of Acceptability of the Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach for topics in Science 8

It can be seen from table 10 that the teacher respondents assessed the developed Enrichment Activities as “Very Highly Acceptable” with an average mean score of 4.80 and it also have “Very Highly Acceptable” results in all Aspect. This implies that the developed Enrichment Activities are found Very Highly Acceptable in terms of Objectives, Contents, Activities, Language and Style, Graphics and Designs and Usefulness. In addition, based on the results it was agreed by the teacher respondents that the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach

were accepted as an effective instructional tool in the teaching and learning process. The result is supported by the study of Bautista (2018) that learning materials being developed taking into consideration the capacity of the learners significantly increased their performance.

Student - Respondents Feedback

The developed Enrichment Activities were found by the student respondents as a useful tool in understanding the topics presented therefore enhances learning because the topics are easy to understand and even magnifies learners' interest in learning the topics because of the simple terms used according to teacher respondents. However, they both recommend that the Enrichment Activities must also provide for more activities outside the classroom and enhanced graphics and designs.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings and in response to the problem posed in the research, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The utilization of Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science improved students' performance.
2. The developed Enrichment Activities is an acceptable teaching tool specifically in Physics.
3. Utilization of Enrichment Activities enhances the learners to think critically.
4. The developed Enrichment Activities guides students towards learning the topics used in the study, fun and enjoyable and guides learning. However, graphics and designs should be enhanced.
5. The developed Enrichment Activities is a useful tool that helps guide the students to learn the concept presented and improve their understanding of the lesson.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are being presented:

1. The teachers may utilize the developed Enrichment Activities in Grade 8 Science utilizing Guided Inquiry Approach as a tool in the teaching and learning process to enhance students' performance.
2. The developed Enrichment Activities may be subjected to revisions and modifications in the future depending on the needs, abilities and learning styles of the learners.
3. The science teachers may develop more teaching materials that will enhance students' performance.
4. The science teachers in any grade level can also use Guided Inquiry Approach in developing instructional materials to make learning fun and enjoyable.
5. The school administrators may provide assistance and give more emphasis on the development of materials that will cater to the needs and abilities of the learners.

6. Further validation of this material may be done by future researchers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the study, the researcher initially sought permission through a letter to the Division Superintendent of the division office where the setting of the study belongs. After the letter was approved by the Division Superintendent the office of the SDS formally forwarded the researcher to the office of the principals of the schools where the study will be conducted with strict compliance to DepEd Order 09, series of 2005. The school principals formally endorsed the researcher to the teachers as a respondent in determining the validity of the materials. The researcher was also assisted by the school head of the school where student respondents belong. The respondents were assured that their participation in the study is voluntary and could withdraw anytime without consequence. The respondents' answers are based on their experiences and no coercion is applied in accomplishing the study. Respondents' names are optional in the survey questionnaire to maintain anonymity. All journals and studies included in the study are in are cited properly.

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